

Supplementary Information to “Integration of *in silico* and *in vitro* data in PBPK modeling for quantitative *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation in risk assessment of food-borne chemicals”

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PBPK model equations

The model is coded as a set of ordinary differential equations. There is one such equation per time-dependent chemical quantity of the model (so-called state variables). There are 13 state variables in the model: the quantity of chemical in venous blood (Q_{ven}), in arterial blood (Q_{art}), in adipose tissues (Q_{fat}), in poorly perfused tissues (Q_{p}), in well perfused tissues (Q_{r}), in liver (Q_{liv}), in unexposed skin ($Q_{\text{s,u}}$), in exposed skin ($Q_{\text{s,e}}$), in the stratum corneum of unexposed skin ($Q_{\text{sc,u}}$), in exposed stratum corneum ($Q_{\text{sc,e}}$), in gut lumen (Q_{gut}), the quantity excreted to urine (Q_{ex}), and the quantity metabolized (Q_{met}). The model can predict, as a function of time, for given oral, dermal and/or inhalation exposures, all the above quantities and the corresponding concentrations as a function of time. Concentrations are obtained by dividing quantities by compartment volumes.

The differential equation for Q_{fat} is:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{fat}}{\partial t} = F_{fat} \cdot \left(C_{art} - \frac{C_{fat}}{PC_{fat}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where F_{fat} is the blood flow to the fat, C_{art} the arterial blood concentration, C_{fat} the concentration in the adipose tissue, and PC_{fat} the fat over blood partition coefficient.

Similar equations are used for the poorly perfused and the richly perfused compartments:

$$\frac{\partial Q_p}{\partial t} = F_p \cdot \left(C_{art} - \frac{C_p}{PC_p} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_r}{\partial t} = F_r \cdot \left(C_{art} - \frac{C_r}{PC_r} \right) \quad (3)$$

In the two above equations, the parameters and variables have the same definitions as in Eq. 1, with a change of subscript.

The differential equation for Q_{gut} is:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{gut}}{\partial t} = Frac \times R_{ing} - k_{gut} \times Q_{gut} \quad (4)$$

where $Frac$ is the fraction of chemical administered orally that is available for absorption (bioavailability), R_{ing} the ingestion rate (quantity ingested per unit time), and k_{gut} the absorption rate (quantity absorbed through the gut wall per unit time).

The time derivative of the quantity metabolized depends on whether linear or saturable kinetics are assumed:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{met}}{\partial t} = \begin{cases} f_{ub} \times CLH \frac{C_{liv}}{PC_{liv}}, & \text{if metabolism is linear} \\ f_{ub} \times V_{liv} \times V_{max} \frac{C_{liv}}{PC_{liv} \times K_m + C_{liv}}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where f_{ub} is the fraction of chemical unbound in blood, CLH the hepatic metabolic clearance, C_{liv} the concentration in liver, PC_{liv} the liver over blood partition coefficient, V_{liv} the liver volume, V_{max} the maximum rate of metabolism, and K_m the Michaelis-Menten constant for metabolism.

The equation for the liver quantity accounts for blood transport, absorption from the gut lumen and metabolism:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{liv}}{\partial t} = F_{liv} \cdot \left(C_{art} - \frac{C_{liv}}{PC_{liv}} \right) + k_{gut} \times Q_{gut} - \frac{\partial Q_{met}}{\partial t} \quad (6)$$

where F_{liv} is the blood flow to the liver.

The equation for the quantity of chemical in the unexposed fraction of the skin stratum corneum is given by:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{sc,u}}{\partial t} = Kp_{sc,vs} \times BSA \cdot (1 - fSA_{exposed}) \times \left(\frac{C_{s,u}}{PC_{sc}} - C_{sc,u} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $Kp_{sc,vs}$ is the diffusion rate of the chemical from stratum corneum to viable skin, BSA the body surface area, $fSA_{exposed}$ the fraction of BSA exposed to the chemical, $C_{s,u}$ the concentration of chemical in the unexposed viable skin, PC_{sc} the viable skin over stratum corneum partition coefficient, and $C_{sc,u}$ the concentration of chemical in the unexposed stratum corneum.

The differential equation for quantity in viable skin unexposed is:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{s,u}}{\partial t} = F_{s,u} \cdot \left(C_{art} - \frac{C_{s,u}}{PC_s} \right) - \frac{\partial Q_{sc,u}}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

where $F_{s,u}$ is the blood flow to the unexposed viable skin, and PC_s the viable skin over blood partition coefficient.

Similarly, for the exposed skin stratum corneum, we have:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{sc,e}}{\partial t} = Kp_{sc,vs} \times BSA \times fSA_{exposed} \cdot \left(\frac{C_{s,e}}{PC_{sc}} - C_{sc,e} \right) + R_{derm} \quad (9)$$

where $C_{s,e}$ the concentration of chemical in the exposed viable skin, $C_{sc,e}$ the concentration in the exposed stratum corneum, and R_{derm} the dermal exposure rate (quantity entering the exposed stratum corneum per unit time).

The differential equation for quantity in viable skin exposed is:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{s,e}}{\partial t} = F_{s,e} \cdot \left(C_{art} - \frac{C_{s,e}}{PC_s} \right) - Kp_{sc,vs} \times BSA \times fSA_{exposed} \cdot \left(\frac{C_{s,e}}{PC_{sc}} - C_{sc,e} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $F_{s,e}$ is the blood flow to the exposed viable skin.

The time evolution quantity of chemical of chemical excreted to urine is governed by:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{ex}}{\partial t} = K_e \times f_{ub} \times C_{art} \quad (11)$$

For the quantity of chemical in arterial blood, we have:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{art}}{\partial t} = F_{alv} \cdot \left(C_{inh} - \frac{C_{art}}{PC_{air}} \right) + F_{blood} \cdot (C_{ven} - C_{art}) - \frac{\partial Q_{ex}}{\partial t} \quad (12)$$

where C_{inh} the concentration of chemical in the air (i.e., inhaled), and PC_{air} the blood over air partition coefficient.

Finally, for the quantity in venous blood:

$$\frac{\partial Q_{ven}}{\partial t} = \sum_i \left(F_i \cdot \frac{C_i}{PC_i} \right) - F_{blood} \times C_{ven} \quad (13)$$

where the indices i include the compartment indices for fat, poorly perfused, richly perfused, liver, skin exposed, and skin unexposed.

List of substance-specific parameters in the PBPK model

Table 1: List of chemical-specific parameters and scaling coefficients of the MCRA "COSMOS" model.

Parameter or scaling coefficient	Symbol	Unit
<i>Partition coefficient related</i>		
Blood / air partition coefficient	PC_{Air}	-
Fat/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Fat}	-
Liver/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Liver}	-
Poorly perfused/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Poor}	-
Richly perfused/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Rich}	-
Viable skin/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Skin}	-
Viable skin/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Skin_sc}	-
Unbound fraction in blood	fub	-
Fraction absorbed by gut	$Frac$	-
Oral absorption rate	$kGut$	1/h
Renal excretion rate	Ke	L/h
Linear metabolism flag	<i>Michaelis</i>	- ^a
Maximum metabolic rate	$Vmax$	mmole/h/L liver
Michaelis-Menten constant	Km	mM
Linear metabolic clearance	CLH	L/h
Skin diffusion coefficient	Kp_sc_vs	dm/h

^a This indicator variable should be set to zero if metabolism is linear and to one if is saturable. In the first case, CLH should be given a value, in the second case $Vmax$ and Km should be given. If there is no metabolism, *Michaelis* should be set to zero and CLH also.

Chemical-specific parameters in the rat models

To fill in.

Determination of in vitro clearances

Different analytical methods had to be developed for dienestrol, imazalil, linuron, cyproconazole, thiacloprid and clothianidin: HPLC with radiochemical detection or DAD detection.

Primary culture of human and animal hepatocytes:

Fresh human or cryopreserved human hepatocytes (laboratory cells bank) were used. For fresh human hepatocytes, the tissue liver was obtained from the Digestive Unit, Archet 2 Hospital, University Hospital of Nice, France. With informed consent of the tissue donor, and following the ethical guidelines, pieces of livers were collected from patient undergoing partial hepatectomy. The studies by Vondran et al. [18] and Hewes et al. [19] report no influence of previous chemotherapy on the isolation outcome or subsequent hepatocytes function. The length of time between chemotherapy and surgery may have allowed functional hepatocyte recovery. Rat and animal hepatocytes were used as after cryopreservation (laboratory cells bank). Cryopreserved hepatocytes were used as previously described in de Sousa et al. [20]. Depending the compound cells were seeded in 48 or 24 multiwell plates in 200 or 500 μ L of culture medium.

Design of experiments

Preliminary experiments have been conducted to determine the concentrations and incubation times that allow the calculation of unchanged product elimination kinetic constants as well as Michaelian constants. Stock solutions and successive dilutions of compounds were prepared in DMSO as a 400 times concentrated solution and then diluted in William's E medium containing no FCS and no phenol red but supplemented with HSA (0.25% DMSO final concentration). Prior to the first experiments, compounds stability in the incubation medium was tested, as well as the nonspecific binding on culture plate. At various intervals times which depend on preliminary experiments, reactions were stopped by addition of 200 μ L (or 500 μ L) of cold acetonitrile. Cells were scraped and stored at -20 °C until analysis. Prior to HPLC analyses the medium/ACN containing cells were submitted to centrifugation to remove proteins. Three to four independent freshly prepared or cryopreserved human and three rat cryopreserved hepatocytes were used for the metabolic study. Radiochemical HPLC methods were developed for imazalil, linuron and cyproconazole ; HPLC DAD method was developed for dienestrol, thiacloprid and clothianidin.

To quantify the number of hepatocytes, 2 to 3 blank wells were fixed with iced MeOH and after coloration by the fluorescent dye HOESCHST 33342, the adherent cells were counted by using an Arrayscan XTI.

Sample and data analysis

The whole hepatocyte extracts from incubations of compounds were analyzed by HPLC with radiochemical detection (Linuron, imazalil, cyproconazole), or DAD detection (dienestrol, thiachlopride, clothianidin) after centrifugation. Unchanged chemicals were quantified.

Data are expressed as mean \pm S.D of at least three independent hepatocyte's experimentations. The data obtained were analyzed based on Michaelis Menten kinetics, substrate velocity curve was calculated using statistical software (Statistica V12.0, Stasoft, France) and used to determine K_m and V_{max} values using nonlinear regression analysis fitting as described in [21]. For dienestrol only intrinsic clearance was determined by fitting $C(t) = C(0) \times e^{-kt}$. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.D.

Results on the *in vitro* metabolism experiments

- Dienestrol (not radiolabelled)

Two concentrations, 10 and 20 μM were tested. Experiments were performed in four different human hepatocytes preparations (higher variability) and three for rats. The mean number of cells for rat was 15.10^3 and 20.10^3 for human. For both cells, 7 times of exposure was tested. The percentage of the unchanged dienestrol versus time was fitted as $C(t) = C(0) \times e^{-kt}$ (Figure 1). The value of k is expressed as ± 0.95 confidence interval which is used to calculate the *in vitro* intrinsic clearance.

Figure 1 :Percent of unchanged dienestrol (mean+/-SD) is fitted in order to determine k (elimination rate constant)

Table 2 : Calculated in vitro intrinsic clearance for rat and human hepatocytes.

<p>Elimination Constant (10μM) = 0.00608</p> <p>Elimination constant (20μM) = 0.00683</p> <p>In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (10μM) = 113.98</p> <p>In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (20μM) = 101.47</p> <p>In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 10μm = 20.26 μl/min/10⁶ cells \pm 1.14</p> <p>In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 20μm = 25.04 μl/min/10⁶ cells \pm 0.86</p>	<p>Elimination Constant (10μM) = 0.00565</p> <p>Elimination constant (20μM) = 0.00505</p> <p>In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (10μM) = 122.65</p> <p>In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (20μM) = 137.27</p> <p>In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 10μm = 14.13 μl/min/10⁶ cells \pm 0.6</p> <p>In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 20μm = 12.63 μl/min/10⁶ cells \pm 0.625</p>
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Imazalil : (¹⁴C radiolabelled compound available)

6 concentrations (0.5 to 100 μ M) were used for incubation times ranging from 30 minutes to 24 hours (Figure 2 and Figure 3). The incubation volume was 250 μ L in 48-well plates for a range of hepatocytes from 75,000 for rats to 100,000 for humans. The appearance of (total) metabolites was modelled to determine the initial velocity at each concentration. These values were then used to determine Km and Vm as described [21].

Figure 2: Rat hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of imazalil metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 3: Human hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentrations versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of imazalil metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Table 3: Calculated V_m and K_m for rat and human hepatocytes

	Rat		Human	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
V_m (nmol/min/number cells)	0.00397 (75000 cells)	0.000230	0.00396(10 ⁵ cells)	0.000372
K_m (µM)	4.295	0.0724	1.959	0.540

Linuron : (¹⁴C radiolabelled compound available)

6 concentrations (1 to 50µM) were used for incubation times ranging from 30 minutes to 24 hours (Figure 4 and Figure 5). The incubation volume was 250µL in 48-well plates for a range of hepatocytes from 75,000 for rats to 100,000 for humans. The appearance of (total) metabolites was modelled to determine the initial velocity at each concentration. These values were then used to determine K_m and V_m as described [21].

Figure 4: Rat hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of linuron metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 5: Human hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of linuron metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Table 4: Calculated Vm and Km for rat and human hepatocytes

	Rat		Human	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
<i>V_m</i> (nmol/min/number cells)	0.0135 (75000 cells)	0.00130	0.0302 (100000 cells)	0.00180
<i>K_m</i> (μM)	9.985	1.609	6.629	0.759

Unbound fractions in hepatocyte incubations were estimated as described in [22] (Table 5).

Table 5 : Unbound fractions in hepatocyte incubations

	Rat (75000 cells for 250μL)	Human (100000 cells for 250μL)
<i>Imazalil</i>	0.78	0.72
<i>Linuron</i>	0.898	0.87

Flutamide metabolism

In vitro metabolism of flutamide was quantified by [15–18] in either rat cells, or human cells, or both. Three metabolic pathways of flutamide were identified, hydroxylation and hydrolysis to Flu-1 and Flu-6. The relative contributions of each pathway depend on the concentration in the liver. The relative contributions are represented in Figure 6, assuming PCLiver=1 and fub=0.05 (intermediate values of QSAR and *in vitro* parameterizations). Hydrolysis to Flu-6 is negligible compared to the other two pathways and realistic internal concentrations. Hydrolysis to Flu-1 also appears to be negligible at hepatic concentrations smaller than 10μM. The concentrations observed in liver in humans and rats in

the data collected were smaller than 1 μM , and therefore the metabolism rate could be approximated by the clearance estimated as hydroxylation V_{max} divided by K_m . However, the predictions using QSAR and in vitro parameters reached predicted concentrations around 10 μM in rats (equivalent to 6.74 with $\text{PCLiver} = 1.48$). In this range of concentrations, although hydroxylation is still the main pathway, metabolism is slightly overestimated when using the clearance value.

Figure 6: Contribution of the three metabolic pathways of flutamide in humans (A) and in rats (B) as a function of the flutamide concentration in liver divided by the blood:liver partition coefficient, which represents the concentration that is available in the liver for metabolism, or venous blood in the liver.

Overall in vitro metabolism data

Table 6: *In vitro* metabolism parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, and imazalil

Compound	V_{max} (pmol/min)	K_m (μM)	Cl_{int} ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells)	Fraction unbound in liver (correction factor for hepatic clearance)	Clearance (L/h)
Flutamide	Flu to 2-Flu-OH	extrapolated		0.665 (httk)	405
	Flu to Flu-1 [23,24]	1900 \pm 100 /mg protein	1100		
	Flu to Flu-6 [25]	1.78 /mg protein	86		
Linuron	30.2 \pm 1.80 /10 ⁵ cells	6.63 \pm 0.760		0.87	580
Dienestrol			14.1 \pm 0.60		157 \pm 6.65
Imazalil	3.95 \pm 0.372 /10 ⁵ cells	1.96 \pm 0.539		0.72	310

Table 7: *In vitro* metabolism parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, and imazalil

Compound	Species	V_{max} (pmol/min)	K_m (μM)	Cl_{int} ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells)	Fraction unbound in liver	Clearance (L/h)
Flutamide	human	Flu to 2-Flu-OH	extrapolated		0.665 (httk)	405

		Flu to Flu-1 [23,24]	1900±100 /mg protein	1100		
		Flu to Flu-6 [25]	1.78 /mg protein	86		
rat		Flu to 2-Flu-OH [26]	282±33 /mg protein	4.03±0.54	0.665 (httk human)	3.63
		Flu to Flu-1 [23,24]	2900±300 /mg protein	1000		
		Flu to Flu-6	extrapolated			
Linuron	human		30.2±1.80 /10 ⁵ cells	6.63±0.760	0.87	580
	rat		13.5±1.29 /75000 cells	9.99±1.61	0.90	1.39
Dienestrol	human			14.1±0.60		157±6.65
	rat			20.3±1.14		1.40±0.079
Imazalil	human		3.95±0.372 /10 ⁵ cells	1.96±0.539	0.72	310
	rat		3.97±0.230 /75000 cells	4.30±0.724	0.78	1.09

PBPK model parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, thiacloprid, clothianidin, and triadimefon

The baseline model was for rat and we extrapolated this to the human by adapting the tissue volumes, blood flows through the tissues and the V_{max} per unit microsomal protein, and the fraction of microsomal protein per organ on the basis of experimental data. Partition coefficients were considered the same for rat and human.

Prostate volume and blood flow were estimated from the reported literature data, for humans [27,28] and for rats [29]. As per requirement of PBPK, these data were converted into fraction of body weight and fraction of cardiac blood flow, respectively.

The chemical-specific parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, thiacloprid, clothianidin, and triadimefon determined in the modified PBPK model were then extracted and used in the generic PBPK as summarized in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** Details on the chemical-specific parameter values and distributions in the modified PBPK model are provided in Appendix 1. The parameters that were adjusted to fit the data were the renal excretion rate (flutamide, clothianidin).

For flutamide, chemical rate constants and metabolic parameters are provided in Table 1 of Appendix 1. The oral absorption process in humans for flutamide was described through a first order absorption rate constant of 0.62 h⁻¹ [30] in both single and multiple oral dose simulations.

We interpreted detailed rat *in vivo* data reported in [31] through a method introduced by [32] and effectively adapted by others [33], This method uses the trapezoidal rule to derive tissue partition coefficients ($K_{i:p}$) from the AUC (area under the curve) observed in *in vivo* animal kinetic profile data of plasma and tissues

$$K_{i:p} = \frac{AUC_{\text{tissue}(0-48)}}{AUC_{\text{plasma}(0-48)}} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where, $AUC_{\text{tissue}(0-48)}$ represents the area under the curve for the tissue concentration-time curves from 0 to 48 h.

The average binding percentage of flutamide with plasma protein was reported for rats and human as 60.6 and 91.9 %, respectively [34]. The reported mean value of 95% for Flu-OH (flutamide hydroxide) for human was used to derive the fraction unbound for Flu-OH, which has also been previously used by [35] for the development of a semi physiologically-based pharmacokinetic model.

We assumed that intracellularly the same fraction of flutamide is bound to intracellular proteins.

Flutamide metabolism is described as a Michaelis-Menten saturable process (Eq.2) with parameters V_{max} (maximum velocity of metabolic reaction) and K_m (1/affinity, i.e. concentration at which reaction occurs at half maximal rate). The reported *in vitro* V_{max} values for the tissue microsomal fraction were scaled to *in vivo* values using the IVIVE approach [36], whereas K_m values were kept the same as the *in vitro* value.

$$v_{A_{\text{mets}}} = \frac{V_{\text{max}} * C_t * f_u}{K_m + C_t * f_u} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where, C_t is the corresponding concentration in tissue and f_u is the fraction unbound.

$v_{A_{\text{mets}}}$ is the rate of production of metabolites.

The *in vitro-in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) approach utilizes physiological specific parameters such as tissue specific microsomal protein content, specific tissue volume and body weight described in Eq. (3) [37,38]. Eq. (3) involves the extrapolation of the specific activity from *in vitro* measured to *in vivo* whole body, used for the both rat and human using species specific

physiological data such as microsomal protein content of tissue, tissue volume and body weight

$$V_{max_{in vivo}} = (V_{max_{in vitro}} * MSPPGT * V_{tissue}) / BW^{.75} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Where, MSPPGT is the microsomal protein per gram tissue; V_{tissue} is the volume of tissue; BW is the body weight and its power to $.75$ is to normalize the scaled V_{max} for different human body weights.

The in-vitro data such as V_{max} and K_m for flutamide metabolism in rats were taken from [39]. This study reported on flutamide metabolism in different tissue cell lines. The *in vitro* measured specific activity (V_{max}) for liver, lung and kidney were scaled to whole body in order to obtain the *in vivo* specific intrinsic clearance. For the development of the human PBPK model, the biochemical parameters such as V_{max} and K_m describing metabolism of flutamide into 3 different metabolites (Figure 7) were taken from in-vitro hepatic cell line studies [24–26]. However, only flutamide hydroxide, which is the major metabolite, was distributed to plasma from the liver site using the same partition coefficient to that of the parent compound. Due to lack of specific data on the generation of different metabolites, no metabolites were included in the current rat PBPK model. However, clearance of flutamide is considered in that model, including its metabolism in rat lung, rat liver and rat kidney as reported by [39] in *in vitro* cell line studies. Elimination rate constants for both flutamide and flutamide hydroxide were visually optimized to fit the plasma data of human studies carried out by Radwanski et al. [40]. The flutamide elimination rate constant was optimized in order to match the observed data knowing the fact that there are some unknown flutamide catabolism pathways.

Figure 7: Schema for human flutamide metabolism; Liver CYP1A2 metabolizes flutamide into flutamide hydroxide, main metabolite. Deacetylation of flutamide by carboxylesterase generates Flu-1. Reduction of aromatic nitro group into amino group by cytochrome reductase results in conversion of Flutamide to FLU-6.

Available in vivo data on kinetics

Table 8: Available *in vivo* data on kinetics

Compound	Organism	Organ / Tissue	Dose	Description of data	Source
Flutamide	human	plasma	250, 500 mg oral	Cmax, AUC	[41]Schulz
		plasma	250 mg/day, oral once then 3 times a day 8 days	0-72 hr after dose	[40]Radwanski [42]Anjum
	rat	plasma	15 mg/kg, oral	0-4 hrs	[43]Zuo
Dienestrol				--	
Linuron				--	
Imazalil	human	urine	0.05 mg/kg, dermal, 8 hours	0-120 hrs	unpublished data (Faniband et al.)
			0.025 mg/kg, oral		
Thiacloprid	rat	organs	1, 5, 100 mg/kg oral	Radioactivity	[44]FAO report (unpublished data)
		plasma	1 mg/kg IV	up to 72 hrs	
		excreta	1 mg/kg/day 14days oral		
Clothianidin	rat	organs, plasma, excreta	2.5, 5, 250 mg/kg oral 25 mg/kg/day 14days oral	Radioactivity up to 168 hrs	[45]FAO report (unpublished data)
		organs	5, 250 mg/kg oral	2, 24, 48 hrs	[46]Yokota
		blood	5 mg/kg oral	5 min to 48 hrs	
Cyproconazole	rat	organs	10 mg/kg, oral + IV	up to 168 hrs	[45]FAO report (unpublished data)
		excreta	0.5 mg/kg/day 7 days oral		
			130mg/kg oral		

Triadimefon / triadimenol	rat	plasma, liver, kidney, brain, fat	50 mg/kg iv	Also TNL dosed in plasma 5min to 24hrs	[47]Crowell
Valproic acid	human	serum	1000 mg twice oral, 900 mg twice iv, 1000 mg iv	0-110 hr	[48]Nitsche
		plasma, blood	600 mg iv, oral	0-28 hrs	[49]Klotz
		plasma	250 mg, oral	0-36 hr,	[50] Chun
		plasma	15 mg/kg, iv	0-6 hrs	[51]Cloyd
	rat	serum	800 mg, oral (and IV)	0-48 hrs	[52]Perucca
		serum	1000 mg, oral	0-48 hrs	[53]Bialer
		plasma	200, 600 mg oral	total and free VPA, 0-24hrs	[54]Binkerd
		plasma	10, 50, 100 mg iv	0-4 hrs	[55]Kobayashi

Modelling uncertainty on chemical-specific parameters

Table 9: *A priori* (expert-based) estimates of uncertainty and variability for PBPK model parameters.

Parameter type	Uncertainty (fold-change)	Variability (fold-change)
Physiological parameters	1.1, 1.2, 1.3	1.1, 1.2
Partition coefficients	3	1.3
Metabolism and transport	3	1.5, 2

In this paper, physiological parameters were set to the values reported in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** No variabilities of physiological of chemical-specific parameters was modelled.

Uncertainty on chemical-specific parameters was modelled using log-normal and truncated log-normal distributions where the standard deviation of the log-transformed parameters was set to $\log(3)$, which is equivalent to a 3 fold deviation on the parameter. In the present report, truncated log-normal distributions were used for the unbound fraction [0;1] and the orally absorbed fraction [0;1] if they were smaller than 0.5. Otherwise, a truncated normal distribution was used. In MCRA on the other hand, the logistic normal distribution is used. As reported in D4.2, to account for the fact that partition

coefficients for a given chemical (in particular when computed with QSAR methods) are typically strongly correlated, they are made proportional to the fat over blood partition coefficient:

$$PC_{fat} = \exp(\log PC_{fat}) \quad (1)$$

$$PC_i = PC_{fat} \times \exp(\log A_i) \quad (2)$$

with $\log A_i$ the log of PC_i over PC_{fat} ratio, and i belonging to set $\{liv, r, p, s, sc\}$ (for liver, richly perfused, poorly perfused, viable skin, and stratum corneum, respectively). Therefore, in the MonteCarlo simulations, PC_{fat} and the scaling factors A_i are lognormally distributed and proportional to each other. Examples of distributions of chemical-specific parameters are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Distribution of a selection of chemical-specific parameters for flutamide in humans with the htkk parameterisation. Estimates for these parameters were the following: $\log_PC_{fat}=4.02$, $CLH=531L/h$, $fub=0.376$, $Frac=1$, $kGut=11/h$, $Ke=7.5L/h$

Parameter distributions in the PBPK models adapted to each compound

Flutamide

Table 10: Flutamide chemical and biochemical specific parameter values and its statistical distributions. LN: LOG NORMAL LN(a,b) means $a = \ln(\text{mean})$ and $b=\text{sd}$ in ln space

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Liver /Plasma	PCLiver		<i>LN</i> (5.57, 1.5)	a
Lung /Plasma	PCLung		<i>LN</i> (1.65, 1.1)	a
Kidney /Plasma	PCKidney	-	<i>LN</i> (2.63, 1.5)	a
Fat/Plasma	PCFat	-	<i>LN</i> (2.78, 1.1)	a
gonads/Plasma	PCGonad	-	<i>LN</i> (1.7, 1.5)	a
prostate/Plasma	PCProstate	-	<i>LN</i> (2.17, 1.1)	a
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	<i>LN</i> (xx, 1.5)	a
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	<i>LN</i> (xx, 1.5)	a
Liver/ Plasma (FLU-OH)	PCLiver	-	<i>LN</i> (5.57, 1.5)	a
<i>Absorption and elimination parameters</i>				
Unbound fraction in plasma (Flutamide)	fup	-	0.09	[34]
Unbound fraction in plasma (Flu-OH)	fup	-	0.05	[35]
Oral absorption rate	kgut	1/h	<i>LN</i> (0.64, 1.1)	a
Elimination rate	kurine	L/h	<i>LN</i> (1.25, 1.5)	optimized
Elimination rate (FLU-OH)	kurineM1	L/h	<i>LN</i> (1.85, 1.5)	optimized
Metabolic parameters for human				
Flu to Flu-OH maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM1_invitro	μg/min/mg MSP	<i>LN</i> (0.079,1.1) ^b	[59]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	mg/L	1.113	[59]

Flu to Flu-6 maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM2_invitro	$\mu\text{g}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ MSP	LN (0.052, 1.1) ^b	[60]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM2	mg/L	23.754	[60]
Flu to Flu-1 maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM3_invitro	$\mu\text{g}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ MSP	LN (0.31, 1.1) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM3	mg/L	82.863	[61]
Total hepatic clearance	CL_H	L/hr	4469.45	Calculated

Metabolic parameters for rat

Unbound fraction in plasma	fu	-	LN (0.4, 1.5)	[34]
Flu metabolism in liver	VmaxlivM1_invitro	$\mu\text{g}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ MSP	LN (0.8, 1.2) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	g/L	0.276	[61]
Flu metabolism in kidney	VmaxkidM1_invitro	$\mu\text{g}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ MSP	LN (0.75, 1.1) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmkidneyM1	g/L	1.6	[61]
Flutamide metabolism in lung	VmaxlungM1_invitro	$\mu\text{g}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ MSP	LN (0.028, 1.1) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmlungM1	g/L	0.193	[61]
Oral absorption rate	kgut	1/h	LN (0.64, 1.1) ^a	optimized
Renal clearance	Cl _R	L/h	LN (0.07, 1.5) ^c	optimized

a: In vivo data of [31] using first order absorption rate constant or AUC ratio for PC.

b; parameters are scaled to whole body species prior to use in model

c Rat glomeration filtration rate was considered

Linuron

Table 11: Linuron specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)	c
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(7.0, 1.1)	c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(2.71, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(81.1, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.01, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/hr	LN(1, 1.5)	
Maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM1_invitro	nmol/min/10 ⁶ cells	LN (0.03,1.1) ^b	In vitro [59]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	Micromole	6.63	In vitro [59]
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	57.4696833	Calculated
Total clearance	kurine*	L/hr	LN(7.62, 1.5)	c

parameters for rat

<i>Partition coefficients</i>					-
fractional unbound	fup	-	1		
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)		c
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(7.0, 1.1)		c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(2.71, 1.1)		c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(81.1, 1.1)		c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.01, 1.1)		c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)		b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)		
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)		
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/hr	LN(1, 1.5)		
Maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM1_invitro	nmol/min/10 ⁶ cells	LN (0.01,1.1) ^b		In vitro [59]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	Micromole	9.98		In vitro [59]
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	0.08		Calculated
Total clearance	kurine	L/hr	LN(0.201, 1.5)		c

b = rest of the body Partition coefficient are set equal to liver

c = parameter are estimated based on QSAR approach and htkk package from R

***scaled from rat Ke value using factor (BMhuman/BMrat)^{0.75}**

Dienestrol

Table 12: Dienestrol specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	LN(0.6, 1.1)	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	c
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(16.14, 1.1)	c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(6.14, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(188, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.45, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	283	In vitro [59]
Total clearance	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(9.48, 1.5)	c
parameters for rat				
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	LN(0.6, 1.1)	

live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	c
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(16.14, 1.1)	c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(6.14, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(188, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.45, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	3	In vitro [59]
Total clearance	Kurine	L/hr	LN(0.25, 1.5)	c

b = rest of the body Partition coefficient are set equal to liver

c = parameter are estimated based on QSAR approach and htk package from R

***scaled from rat Ke value using factor (BMhuman/BMrat)^{0.75}**

Clothianidin

Table 13: Clothianidin specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	-
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(0.2, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(1.80, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(0.39, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(0.86, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	b
<i>Absorption and elimination parameters</i>				
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearence parameters for rat	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(2.27, 1.5)	a
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	-
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(0.2, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(1.80, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(0.39, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(0.86, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma	PCRestBody	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	b

partition coefficient

Absorption and elimination parameters

Absorption rate constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearance	kl _{urine}	L/hr	LN(0.06, 1.5)	a

*scaled from rat K_e value using factor $(BM_{human}/BM_{rat})^{0.75}$

Thiaclopid

Table 14: Thiaclopid specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
Partition coefficients				-
fractional unbound	fup		1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		LN(2.60, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain		LN(0.67, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney		LN(1.67, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat		LN(1.23, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad		LN(0.51, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		LN(2.60, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearence	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(2.27, 1.5)	a
Rat parameters				
Partition coefficients			-	
fractional unbound	fup		1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		LN(2.60, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain		LN(0.67, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney		LN(1.67, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat		LN(1.23, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad		LN(0.51, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		LN(2.60, 1.5)	b

Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearence	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(0.060, 1.5)	a

a = partition coefficient are estimated based on AUC method from rat in-vivo studies and total clearance is visually fitted against in-vivo data

***scaled from rat Ke value using factor $(BM_{human}/BM_{rat})^{0.75}$**

Triadimefon

Table 15: Kinetic parameters for for Triadimefon and Triadimenol

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values	References
<i>Triadimefon Partition coefficients</i>				
Liver plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		1.25	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Brain Plasma partition coefficient	PCBrain		0.97	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney		1.32	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat		13.47	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		1.32	(Crowell et al., 2011)
<i>Triadimenol Partition coefficients</i>				
Live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		6.98	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCBrain		2.76	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Fat plasm partition coefficient	PCKidney		4.54	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Brain Plasma partition coefficient	PCFat		1.18	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		2.76	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Metabolic parameter for Triadimefon				
Triadimefon reduction to Triadimenol	Vmax	$\mu\text{mole /h/kg}^{.75}$	556.4	(Crowell et al., 2010)
Triadimefon reduction to Triadimenol	Km	$\mu\text{mole /L}$	47.3	(Crowell et al., 2010)
Triadimenol oxidation to Triadimefon	Vmax	$\mu\text{mole /h/kg}^{.75}$	278.2	(Crowell et al., 2010)
Triadimenol oxidation to Triadimefon	Km	$\mu\text{mole /L}$	31.5	(Crowell et al., 2010)

Table 16: Imazalil-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for rats.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	297.18	(pearce et al. 2017)
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (36.5, 3)	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	-	0.0175	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fub</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.036 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.8 , 1.2)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (1, 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (0.09, 1.5)	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (6, 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.00002, 1.5)	- ^d

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These value are baseline vales, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by diving *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the human data.

^e Set to the glomerular filtration rate.

Table 17: Imazalil-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for humans.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	297.18	(pearce et al. 2017)
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (36.5, 3)	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / strateum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>		0.0175	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fub</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.015, 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017) ^d
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.8, 1.2)	- ^d
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (10, 1.5)	- ^d
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (17, 1.5)	- ^d
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (50, 1.5)	- ^d
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.00002, 1.5)	- ^d

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These value are baseline vales, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by diving *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data (see text and Table 5).

Cyproconazole

Table 18: Cyproconazole-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for rats.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	291.78	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (7.1, 3)	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	-	0.028	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.11 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.996 , 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (1, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (0.21, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.1, 2.0)	- ^e

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These value are baseline vales, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by diving *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Table 19: Cyproconazole-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for humans.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	291.78	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (7.1, 3)	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>		0.028	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.07, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.996, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (1, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (23.4, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.1, 2)	- ^e

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Valproic acid

Table 20: Valproic acid-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for rats.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	144.21	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.16, 3)	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.28	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.36	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	-	1.56	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.14, 1.5)	(Pearce et al., 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.996, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (0.3, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	0.4	- ^d
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.1, 2.0)	- ^e

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Table 21: Valproic acid-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for humans.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	144.21	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.16, 3)	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.28	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.36	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>		1.56	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.14, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.996, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (2.88, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (8.8, 1.5)	- ^d
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.1, 2)	- ^e

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Verification of the PBPK model using data on kinetics in humans

Parameters from htk package

Figure 9: Predicted blood and observed plasma concentrations for flutamide (A) (data from [25], 250 mg/day, oral once then 3 times a day 8 days) and valproic acid (B) (data from [37], 1000 mg, oral) **httk parameterization in humans**. Large black line= median MC prediction, large grey lines= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions. 10 different MC predictions are represented in grey. Narrow black line= prediction without variability.

Figure 10: Predicted and observed cumulated urinary excretion of imazalil (A, B: dermal exposure, C, D: oral exposure), **httk parameterization in humans**

Parameters from QSAR models

Figure 11: Predicted blood and observed plasma concentrations for flutamide (A) (data from [25], 250 mg/day, oral once then 3 times a day 8 days) and valproic acid (B) (data from [37], 1000 mg, oral) QSAR parameterization in humans. Large black line= median MC prediction, large grey lines= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions. 10 different MC predictions are represented in grey. Narrow black line= prediction without variability.

Figure 12: Predicted and observed cumulated urinary excretion of imazalil, (A, B: dermal exposure, C, D: oral exposure), QSAR parameterization in humans

Parameters from QSAR models and in vitro measurements

Figure 13: Predicted blood and observed plasma concentrations for flutamide (A) (data from [25], 250 mg/day, oral once then 3 times a day 8 days) and valproic acid (B) (data from [37], 1000 mg, oral) QSAR + in vitro parameterization in humans

Figure 14 : Predicted and observed cumulated urinary excretion of imazalil (A, B: dermal exposure, C, D: oral exposure), QSAR + in vitro parameterization in humans

Verification of the PBPK model using data on kinetics in rats

Parameters from htkk package

Figure 15: Valproic acid blood concentrations after an oral dose of 200mg/kg, 600mg/kg, or an intravenous dose of 100mg/kg, **htkk parameterization in rats**. In the first two figures, data for total and unbound VPA are represented. The black dashed line represents the prediction for unbound VPA. MC simulations are only represented for total VPA.

Figure 16: Triadimefon concentration in blood after a 50 mg/kg BW IV dose, **htkk parameterization, rats**

Figure 17: Cyproconazole blood and tissue concentrations following 7 daily doses of 0.5mg/kg BW, **httk parameterization in rats**. Points represent radioactivity expressed as equivalents of administered dose

Figure 18: Thiaclopid blood and tissue concentrations after a single or 14 daily doses of 1mg/kg BW, **httk parameterization in rats**. Points represent radioactivity expressed as equivalents of administered dose, Red=Females, Blue = Males.

Figure 19: Flutamide concentration in blood after a single oral dose of 15mg/kg BW of flutamide, [httpk parameterization in rats](#)

Parameters from QSAR models

Figure 20: Valproic acid blood concentrations after an oral dose of 200mg/kg, 600mg/kg, or an intravenous dose of 100mg/kg, **QSAR parameterization in rats**. In the first two figures, data for total and unbound VPA are represented. The black dashed line represents the prediction for unbound VPA. MC simulations are only represented for total VPA.

Figure 21: Cyproconazole blood and tissue concentrations following 7 daily doses of 0.5mg/kg BW, **QSAR parameterization in rats**. Points represent radioactivity expressed as equivalents of administered dose

Figure 22: Triadimefop concentration in blood after a 50 mg/kg BW IV dose, **QSAR parameterization, rats**

Figure 23: Thiocloprid blood and tissue concentrations after a single or 14 daily doses of 1mg/kg BW, **QSAR parameterization in rats**. Points represent radioactivity expressed as equivalents of administered dose, Red=Females, Blue = Males.

Figure 24: Flutamide concentration in blood after a single oral dose of 15mg/kg BW of flutamide, **QSAR parameterization, rats**

Parameters from QSAR models and in vitro measurements

Figure 25: Valproic acid blood concentrations after an oral dose of 200mg/kg, 600mg/kg, or an intravenous dose of 100mg/kg, QSAR + in vitro parameterization in rats. In the first two figures, data for total and unbound VPA are represented. The black dashed line represents the prediction for unbound VPA. MC simulations are only represented for total VPA.

Figure 26: Cyproconazole blood and tissue concentrations following 7 daily doses of 0.5mg/kg BW, QSAR + in vitro parameterization in rats. Points represent radioactivity expressed as equivalents of administered dose

Figure 27: Triadimefion concentration in blood after a 50 mg/kg BW IV dose, **QSAR+ in vitro parameterization, rats**

Figure 28: Thiacloprid blood and tissue concentrations after a single or 14 daily doses of 1mg/kg BW, **QSAR + in vitro parameterization in rats**. Points represent radioactivity expressed as equivalents of administered dose, Red=Females, Blue = Males.

Figure 29: Flutamide concentration in blood after a single oral dose of 15mg/kg BW of flutamide, QSAR+ in vitro parameterization, rats

Predictions vs. observations for compounds for which kinetics were reported as total radioactivity

Table 22: Available *in vivo* data on kinetics, obtained using radioactivity

Compound	Organism	Organ / Tissue	Dose	Description of data	Source
Thiacloprid	rat	organs	1, 5, 100 mg/kg oral	Radioactivity	[44]FAO report (unpublished data)
		plasma	1 mg/kg IV	up to 72 hrs	
		excreta	1 mg/kg/day 14days oral		
Clothianidin	rat	organs, plasma, excreta	2.5, 5, 250 mg/kg oral 25 mg/kg/day 14days oral	Radioactivity	[45]FAO report (unpublished data)
		organs	5, 250 mg/kg oral	2, 24, 48 hrs	[46]Yokota
		blood	5 mg/kg oral	5 min to 48 hrs	
Cyproconazole	rat	organs	10 mg/kg, oral + IV	up to 168 hrs	[45]FAO report (unpublished data)
		excreta	0.5 mg/kg/day 7 days oral		
			130mg/kg oral		

Figure 30: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for thiacloprid administered in 1, 5, and 100mg/kg BW single oral doses, 1mg/kg BW /day repeated oral doses, or 1mg/kg single IV dose.. Grey lines are used to show that the observations represent the parent compound and metabolites and that the parent compound concentrations are actually equal or smaller than the data points reported. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters, D) in vivo parameterisation.

Figure 31: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for clothianidin administered in 2.5, 5, and 250 mg/kg BW single oral doses and 25 mg/kg BW /day repeated oral doses, and for cyproconazole administered in 10 and 130 mg/kg single oral doses, 10mg/kg BW single IV doses, 0.5mg/kg BW/day repeated oral doses. Grey lines are used to show that the observed concentrations of the parent compound are equal or smaller than the data points reported. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters D) in vivo parameterisation.

Predictions of human blood concentrations under continuous 100-day exposure scenarios

Figure 1: **QSAR** parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of **humans** to 1mg/kg/day. **Black**: predictions without variability. **Red**: = median MC prediction. **Grey**= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions.

Figure 2: htk parameterisation predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure to 1mg/kg/day in humans. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 3: QSAR + in vitro parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of humans to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 4: *in vivo* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of humans to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 5: QSAR parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 6: *httk* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 7: QSAR + *in vitro* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 8: *in vivo* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Predictions of rat blood concentration for a continuous 100-day exposure to 1mg/kg/day of each chemical independently

Figure 9: **httk** parameterisation predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure to 1mg/kg/day in rats. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions.

Figure 10: QSAR parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions.

Figure 11: QSAR + *in vitro* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions.

